

Microwave-mediated Green chemistry approach for the synthesis of some chalcone derivatives and evaluation of their anthelmintic activity

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In the present study, microwave-mediated Green chemistry approach is followed to prepare some chalcone derivatives. For this purpose, microwave heating technology is used as the alternative energy sources to synthesize a series of chalcone derivatives by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution followed by dehydration. With the help of microwave, the rate of reaction is increased with less byproduct formation and better yield of the product. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds are confirmed by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectra and CHN analyses. The titled compounds are screened for their anthelmintic activity and significant activity as compared to the standard drug is found. Compounds with electron withdrawing groups are found to be highly potent among the series.

Keywords: Anthelmintic activity, chalcone, Claisen-Schmidt reaction, Green chemistry, microwave, synthesis.

1. Introduction

Chalcone consists of 1,3-diphenyl-2-propene-1-one framework with two aromatic rings such as A and B. It is also known as α,β -unsaturated ketone¹⁻³. The biological activity of chalcone is due to presence of an enone (-CO-CH=CH-) pharmacophore in their structures⁴ as depicted in Fig. 1. The chalcone and their derivatives act as key intermediates during synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds which possess broad spectrum of biological activities such as antibac-

Fig. 1. Structure and 3D property of chalcone showing plane, centroid and exclusion sphere.

terial, antifungal, anti-tubercular, antitumor, anthelmintic, analgesic and inflammatory, etc.⁵⁻⁷ as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Clinically used drugs containing chalcone moiety.

The chalcone derivatives are prepared by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate with

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of chalcone derivatives.

various aldehydes in the presence of ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution followed by dehydration⁸⁻¹² (Scheme 1). With the help of microwave heating methodology, there is decrease in reaction times with increased product yields and enhanced product purity by reducing unwanted side reactions as compared to conventional synthesis¹³⁻¹⁸. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds are confirmed by FT-IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectra and CHN analyses. The titled compounds are screened for their anthelmintic activity.

2. Experimental

All chemicals were of synthetic grade (S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Mumbai, India). The synthesized products were recrystallized from ethanol as a solvent. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes, expressed in °C and are uncorrected. The time required for completion of the reaction and the purity of the compounds were checked by TLC using percolated silica gel-G plates and spots were observed by exposure to iodine vapors or by UV light. The compounds were characterized by using IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analysis. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on Shimadzu IR affinity using KBr discs and the values are expressed in cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal

standard in DMSO-*d*₆. Elemental analyses of the newly synthesized compounds were carried out on Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer.

2.1. Synthesis of ethyl-4-aminobenzoate (2):

Para-amino-benzoic acid (0.01 m, 1.37 g) was dissolved ethanol (0.01 m, 0.46 g). To this, concentrated sulfuric acid was added slowly with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC. After completion of the reaction, white colored product of ethyl 4-aminobenzoate (2) was obtained.

2.2. Synthesis of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate (3):

Ethyl 4-aminobenzoate (0.01 m, 1.65 g) in 25 ml of ethanol was taken in a round bottom flask. To this, acetyl chloride (0.01 m, 0.78 g) was added drop wise with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h in a water bath. The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC. After completion of the reaction, it was cooled to get the solid product of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate (3).

2.3. Conventional synthesis of chalcone derivatives (4a-e):

To the solution of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate (0.01 m, 2.07 g) in absolute ethanol (25 ml), various aromatic alde-

Table 1. Physical properties for compound (4a-e)

Compd. code	Ar	M.W. (g/mol)	Color	R _f value	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
4a	C ₆ H ₅ -	219.24	Gray	0.58	198–200	62
4b	4Cl-C ₆ H ₅ -	295.33	Brown	0.64	290–293	68
4c	3NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅ -	340.33	Brown	0.62	261–269	63
4d	4NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅ -	340.33	Brown	0.63	240–249	74
4e	(CH ₃) ₂ -NH-	338.4	Yellow	0.64	265–268	81

hydres (0.01 m) were added in the presence of NaOH. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h on water bath. The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC. After completion of the reaction, it was cooled in an ice bath get the solid product of chalcone.

2.4. Microwave synthesis of chalcone derivatives (4a-e):

To the solution of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate (0.01 m, 2.07 g) in absolute ethanol (25 ml), various aromatic aldehydes (0.01 m) were added in the presence of NaOH. The reaction mixture was irradiated under microwave for 4–8 min at power level 2 (240 watt). The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC. After completion of the reaction, it was cooled on an ice bath get the solid product of chalcone.

3. Anthelmintic activity

Indian adult earthworms of the genus and species, *Pheritima posthuma* (family: Megascleidae), were used to study the anthelmintic activity. The earthworms were collected from the water logged areas of soils in Nunna, Andhra Pradesh, India were washed with normal saline to remove all the fecal matter and waste surrounding their body. The earth worms (*Pheritima posthuma*) 5–8 cm in length and 0.2–0.3 cm width weighing 0.8–3.04 g were used for all experiment protocols. The earthworms resembled the intestinal roundworm parasites of human beings both anatomically and physiologically and hence were used to study the anthelmintic activity^{19–22}.

Procedure:

Gum acacia solution (1%) was prepared in normal saline. Test solutions were prepared by using this solution. Sample were taken in petriplates and adult healthy earth

worms (n = 6) were introduced in to them^{23–25}. Observations were made for the time taken to paralyze and time taken for death of the organism. Paralysis was said to occur when the worms do not review even in normal saline. Death was concluded when worms lost their motility followed by fading away of the body color, and the values are summarized^{26–28}.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Chemical synthesis:

Various chalcone derivatives were synthesized by reaction of ethyl 4-acetamidobenzoate with various aromatic aldehydes in presence of NaOH through Claisen-Schmidt condensation. The yield of final product obtained was 72–81%. All the synthesized compounds were soluble in methanol, and dimethyl sulphoxide and insoluble in water, and ethanol, benzene. The spectra show usually a peak, near 1625–1650 cm⁻¹, characteristic of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl (ketone) group. The IR spectrum of chalcone derivatives showed absorption at λ_{max} at 1536 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nitro), 1178.91 cm⁻¹ (-C-O), 2924–3316 cm⁻¹ (aromatic-CH), 3029.39 cm⁻¹ (=C-H), 3305.35 cm⁻¹ (-NH). In the ¹H NMR spectrum, the aromatic protons were seen as a multiplet at δ 6.86–8.56 (m, 8H, Ar-H). The proton of the =CH and -NH resonated as a sharp singlet at δ 9.79 and 11.36 respectively. The protons of -CH₂CH₃ showed triplet at δ 2.50–2.51. The mass spectra of the chalcone derivative showed molecular ion peak corresponding to their molecular formula. Compound **4b** and **4e** showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 296.35 and 340.11 respectively.

4.2. Anthelmintic activity:

All newly synthesized chalcone derivatives were evaluated for anthelmintic activity at the concentration of 100 μ g/

Table 2. Elemental analysis of titled compounds (**4a-e**)

Compd. code	Elemental analysis							
	Calcd. (%)				Found (%)			
	C	H	N	O	C	H	N	O
4a	65.74	5.98	6.39	21.89	65.72	5.94	6.35	21.84
4b	73.20	5.80	4.74	16.25	73.22	5.82	4.72	16.23
4c	63.52	4.74	8.23	23.51	63.50	4.72	8.21	23.50
4d	63.52	4.74	8.23	23.51	63.53	4.72	8.22	23.50
4e	70.99	6.55	8.28	14.18	70.95	6.53	8.26	14.16

Table 3. Anthelmintic activity of chalcone derivatives (**4a-e**)

Sl. No.	Treatment groups	Dose (mg/ml)	Paralysis time (min)	Death time (min)
1.	4a	100	24	28
2.	4b	100	27	29
3.	4c	100	25	27
4.	4d	100	22	22
5.	4e	100	26	23
6.	Control	Normal saline	–	–
7.	Albendazole	100	17	20

ml and the results were compared with standard Albendazole as depicted in Fig. 3. Among the tested compounds, compound **4c**, **4d** and **4e** exhibited significant activity as compared to standard drug (Albendazole). The order of anthelmintic activity of synthesized compounds against *Pheritima posthuma* is **4d** > **4e** > **4c** > **4a** > **4b**.

Fig. 3. Anthelmintic activity of chalcone derivatives.

Conclusion

The new generations of chalcone derivative would represent fruitful matrix for further development of better medi-

cal agents. Microwave-mediated Green chemistry approach acts as an important tool for medicinal chemists to develop newer compounds possessing chalcone moiety that could be better agents in terms of efficacy and safety. Chalcones are unique moieties which are associated with several biological activities. Further investigations must be carried out to evaluate more biological activities of chalcone derivative. Thus the quest to explore many more modifications on chalcone moiety needs to be continued for the use of mankind. Further experiments are needed to elucidate their mechanism of action.

Abbreviations

Cl: Chloro, °C: Degrees Celsius, F: Fluoro, h: Hour, IR: Infrared, KBr: Potassium bromide, MF: Molecular formula, mg: Milligram, ml: Milliliters, MHz: Megahertz, MWI: Microwave irradiation, NO₂: Nitro, nm: Nanometre, NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance, OH: Hydroxy, ppm: Parts per million, % : Percent, S.E.M: Standard Error Mean, TLC: Thin layer chromatography, TMS: Tetramethylsilane, W: Watt.

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